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Executive summary

Portugal has undertaken an ambitious digitalisation agenda through flagship programmes such as InCoDe.2030 (the National Digital Competences Initiative) and the Indústria 4.0 strategy. These initiatives aim to accelerate digital skills and technology adoption in industry, specially manufacturing given the sector's importance for the economy^a, as part of the EU Digital Decade objectives. Digital adoption and training have been heavily concentrated in greater urban areas, while many rural and interior areas remain at the periphery of the transition – also linked to the manufacturing fabric and territorial distribution in the country. Large companies and high-tech sectors disproportionately attract investment and skilled workers, whereas small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and traditional industries struggle with access to funding, skills acquisition and managerial capacity.

This case study finds that key drivers of inequality are embedded in policy design and implementation: fragmented governance and frequent reshuffling of responsibilities create coordination failures; infrastructure deployment is geographically universal but digital usage remains uneven due to socio-demographic factors; public funding and support programmes tend to favour larger and better-resourced companies.

Drawing on policy documents, data and stakeholder interviews, this analysis argues that Portugal's digital policies lack efficient coordination and funding mechanisms tailored to local realities, creating and reproducing pre-existing equity deficits in practice. We identify five principal inequality drivers: (1) institutional fragmentation and weak governance arrangements; (2) geographic concentration of economic dynamism; (3) financial and funding schemes reaching unevenly local actors; (4) difficulties to match reskilling and upskilling processes with labour market dynamics; and (5) automation and AI influence influencing pace of digital transition.

^a Manufacturing sector represents over 90% of industrial production in Portugal, with a key role emphasising the quality of skills, wages and productivity in Portugal (Ferraz, 2024).

1 Introduction

Historically, industrial transformations have required **shifts in workforce skills**. Today, the digitalisation is transforming industries globally, with the manufacturing sector undergoing significant changes under Industry 4.0. Known as the fourth industrial revolution, industry 4.0 refers to the integration of digital technologies into manufacturing and industrial processes. It highlights the role of these technologies in driving productivity, efficiency, and flexibility while enabling smarter decision-making and customisation in manufacturing¹.

Industry 4.0 has intensified the digital divide^b. Automation and interconnected systems require not only Information and Communication Technology (ICT) literacy but also advanced skills like data analysis, cybersecurity and system integration.² However, the divide is a multidimensional issue encompassing disparities in usage (i.e. use of digitally-enabled technologies), abilities (to use such technologies) and benefits derived from digitalisation³. Large segments of the workforce are at risk of exclusion from economic opportunities the digitalisation offers, exacerbating inequalities. The digital divide seems to be rooted in structural inequalities. As one stakeholder noted, *“outside the cities, digitalisation is very low”*. Rural areas may technically be “connected,” but adoption lags because local communities include many retirees, early school-leavers and smallholder enterprises for whom digital technologies seem less relevant. In fact, infrastructure is necessary but insufficient; without complementary economic activity, education and support, rural regions remain on the ‘wrong side’ of the digital divide.

In Europe, over 90% of professional roles demand basic digital knowledge⁴. However, about 42% of Europeans, including 37% of the workforce, lack fundamental digital skills. **European policy frameworks** (e.g. Digital Europe Programme, European Skills Agenda, Digital Education Action Plan, Digital skills and jobs coalition, etc.) have prioritised addressing the digital skills gap with ambitious targets. For instance, the European Skills Agenda and the Digital Education Action Plan⁵ aim to ensure 70% of Europeans possess basic digital skills by 2025, with an 80% target by 2030. In direct link with industries, European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH) work as local markets in which pool of experts assist companies and public administration in addressing digital challenges and transformation. Despite Europe’s progress through multiple initiatives at different levels (EU, national, regional or local), a persistent digital skills gap threatens industrial competitiveness and exacerbates societal inequalities.

If we look at the Portuguese case, the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) reveals that 26% of the Portuguese population in 2019 had no digital skills (9% in the EU as a whole) and that 52% had only basic digital skills (58% on average in the EU). While there is a growing pattern of digitalisation, **Portugal is still lagging in most intermediate rankings** compared to other European countries (see Figure 1 below).

The gap between individual digital skills^c could be assessed along different pathways. One is the relation between age, education and gender. In Portugal, the percentage of people with

^b The digital divide refers to multi-dimensional inequalities in access to, use of, and outcomes from digital technologies, shaped by socio-economic, geographic, and educational factors (OECD, 2001; van Dijk, 2006).

^c Overall digital skills are assessed across five component indicators: (1) information and data literacy, (2) communication and collaboration, (3) digital content creation, (4) problem-solving, and (5) safety. Individuals

above-basic digital skills is higher among 16 to 24-year-old individuals with high formal education (70%), followed by those between 25 and 54 years old (62%). Young age and high formal education have a significant impact on the level of digital skills, whereas **with increasing age, there is a decrease in digital skills**. A transversal decrease in digital skills literacy is observed in older and less educated groups. When examining gender and age, women tend to have higher digital skills compared to men in the 25 -34 age group. However, when looking in older age groups, a higher percentage of men display basic or above-basic skills, while a higher percentage of women have limited digital skills. Another interesting gap is between the living areas of the Portuguese citizens. **Higher levels of digital skills are performed by people living in cities** (34% individuals with above basic digital skills), compared to the 26% and 21% of people living in suburbs and towns.

Figure 1 Advanced skills and development in Portugal vs EU27; Source: DESI)

These results are compounded by Portugal’s dual labour market, in which a large proportion of workers – young people in particular – are employed on temporary contracts and therefore face greater job insecurity, lower job quality and fewer education and training opportunities⁶. The technological changes are creating further pressure on the growing labour market not only through the skills gap across different groups of workers but also across workers in specific sectors. The manufacturing sector is the case in point in for Portugal.

The manufacturing sector, a traditionally skills-intensive one, is under increasing pressure to digitalise processes, integrate artificial intelligence and adopt (semi-)automated systems. Industry 4.0 demands a range of digital skills. Operators need basic ICT proficiency to interact with advanced machinery, while engineers and managers require advanced skills to design, implement, and oversee digital systems⁷. The absence of workers with the requisite skills threatens productivity and innovation. The picture is promising in terms of progress of gaining

are classified as having: above basic skills if all five indicators are at above-basic level; basic skills if all five are at least basic but not all above basic; low skills if four of five are at least basic; narrow skills if three of five are at least basic; limited skills if two of five are at least basic; and no digital skills if fewer than two indicators reach basic level.

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Figure 2 below), evidencing improvement in upskilling. However, ***what are the explicit and hidden inequalities emerging from the policy implementation of digital transition processes in the manufacturing sector?***

Figure 2 Percentage of individuals with digital skills working in manufacturing sector; Source: EUROSTAT)

This case study aims to **analyse the inequality drivers of the digital transition policy in Portugal**, by examining the national initiatives directed towards bridging the gap on digital skills in the manufacturing sector. The focus will be on the Indústria 4.0 initiative within broader national policies for skilling, reskilling and upskilling (InCoDe.2030 national programme). Portugal's **Industry 4.0 initiative** aims to support manufacturing by fostering skills development. It combines public and private efforts to train workers in areas such as cybersecurity, IoT, and data science. This initiative is part of a broader strategy: the National Plan for Digital Transitions, developed in 2020 by the government of Portugal in compliance with the European policy directives on digital transitions.

The Portuguese case is selected as it depicts both progress and bottlenecks in the design and implementation of digital transition policy. The country performs at better than average level among European countries, but still lags in medium rankings (e.g. DESI). The case study will have a mixed methodological approach including an initial phase of desk research based on available policy documents at European and national level (both in English and Portuguese), followed by a series of semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders (national ministries and agencies, DIHs, training providers and researchers), looking to gather further qualitative insights on challenges and opportunities to tackle inequalities in I4.0 skills demand-supply divergence.

2 The digital transition policy process

The government of Portugal initiated the policy design to address the challenges of digital transformation across society, the economy and public services. These challenges include low digital literacy, lack of widespread of digital skills and the need for competitiveness in a digital economy. The urgency for digital transformation gained prominence during the COVID-19 pandemic, which highlighted the need for robust digital infrastructures and skills – becoming a pivot point for **setting the topic in the agenda** and reinforcing initiatives supporting the transformation.

2.1 Digital policy design

The **Action Plan for Digital Transition (APDT)** was a response to the broader objectives of the European Union's Digital Decade, aiming to ensure that digital opportunities are accessible to all citizens and organizations in Portugal. The APDT was approved by the Council of Ministers' Resolution No. 30/2020⁸, aligning with Portugal's strategic response to the EU's Digital Decade goals. The agenda reflects societal and economic pressures to adapt to increasing digitalisation, alongside labour market changes due to automation. The digital transformation process encompassed several initiatives around digital skills for citizens and workers, business digital transformation and digitalisation of public services.

Figure 3 Pillars of digital transition strategy in Portugal (Source: Ponto Digital)

Building skills is mostly represented under pillar one **policy design**, that focuses on promoting digital inclusion. It includes initiatives such as “Eu Sou Digital” (I am digital), which trains volunteer mentors to help adults with low or no digital literacy learn basic online skills, and the “Centro Internet Segura,” which raises awareness and offers support on safe and responsible internet use. It also encompasses the “INCoDe.2030” programme, aimed at

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fostering digital skills across education, training, and employment, and “Emprego + Digital,” which offers training to workers to strengthen their digital competencies. These measures collectively target different segments of the population — from children and students to workers and seniors — ensuring that the development of digital skills is widespread across Portuguese society.

Under pillar two **policy design**, the government supports actions that place **national companies in a new paradigm of development and competitiveness**, facilitating their transition to digital. The focus is based on measures that provide support for investment and encouragement of the digitalisation of companies and awareness and training, particularly of micro and SMEs, which represent much of the business fabric and employment in Portugal. It also contributed to making the entrepreneurship ecosystem more dynamic and mobilising startups, as well as developing of initiatives that contribute to the adoption and consolidation of scientific and technological knowledge in business activity.

The figure below presents the **strategy for industries from digitalisation to innovation** through different phases (mobilising, training, planning, transforming, valorising) and by understanding the role of support to people and skills as well as the supporting actions for companies.

Figure 4 Digital transformation pathways for enterprises; Source: “Portugal, Nação Digital – 2 anos de Transição Digital”

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However, several initiatives were relevant to bridge the gap between digital skills and labour market - mainly under pillar one and two -, namely:

- **INCoDe.2030:** Promotes digital literacy, digital workforce upskilling, and lifelong learning. In the context of INCoDe.2030 programme, the government launched the ***Dynamic Reference Framework for Digital Competence*** (QDRCD)^d, an instrument for assessing the population's digital skills. Based on the European Digital Competence Framework for Citizens, the QDRCD has three main objectives: to support the definition of policies and strategies; to design education programmes; and to assess and certify skills, either through self-diagnosis or through certifying bodies.
- **AI Portugal 2030:** Encourages AI adoption and innovation through collaboration between academia and businesses, targeting startups, SMEs, and research institutions. This programme aims to enable the development of transferable skills from academia to industry, through effective acquisition by learners in academia, in close cooperation with companies and the public administration.
- **UPskill:** this programme aims to retrain people – unemployed or underemployed – in various areas of ICT. Companies operating in the national market identify technological areas and job vacancies, according to their actual talent needs. People from areas considered to have low employability or subject to pressure from automation are challenged to join a retraining process and become active players in the various areas of ICT.
- **Comercio Digital:** this project aims to promote a new paradigm of training and qualification of SMEs through the development of new capabilities and transformations in the digital economy. The project hosts learning sessions and workshops in cooperation with business and commercial associations to support the transition to SMEs into the digital commerce.
- **Indústria 4.0 Programme:** Focuses on accelerating the adoption of digital technologies and re-skilling 200,000 workers.

Despite this elaborated strategy, interviews revealed limitations in the vision-to-implementation pathway. The initiatives were described as “an aggregation of cumulative actions” constructed without broad consultation. Its initial rollout notably lacked a clear budget: ministries and agencies were expected to fund initiatives out of their own allocations, leading to stakeholder to commit their own resources. One interviewee noted that without dedicated funding, early projects proceeded “only because people volunteered their own resources.” In this direction, the digital transition policy design operated mostly as a policy umbrella, rather than a supportive policy aligned with funding mechanisms.

The following section will deep dive into Indústria 4.0 programme, as main initiative linking digital transition processes applied to manufacturing sector in Portugal.

^d The document was developed in collaboration with the National Agency for Qualification and Vocational Education (ANQEP), the Directorate-General for Education (DGE), the Directorate-General for Qualification of Workers in Public Functions (INA), the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), the Institute for Employment and Vocational Training (IEFP) and António Moreira and Margarida Lucas from the University of Aveiro.

2.1.1 Indústria 4.0

The “Indústria 4.0” programme⁹ aims to identify Portuguese’s industry needs in the i4.0 context and guide public and private actions to foster its acceleration. It has three main objectives:

- Accelerate the adoption of i4.0 by the Portuguese business community
- Promote Portuguese technology providers as i4.0 players
- Making Portugal an attractive hub for investment in i4.0

In its **first phase (2017–2019)**, the Indústria 4.0 programme aimed to accelerate the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies and concepts in the Portuguese industrial system, position the country as an attractive destination for investment in this context, and promote Portuguese technological companies at the international level. To achieve these goals, the programme followed a bottom-up design involving industry, academia, and education stakeholders, and was structured into sixty-four public and private measures organised around six strategic axes: human resources development, collaborative ecosystem, start-up I4.0, financing and investment, internationalisation, and legal and regulatory adaptation.

The first phase of the Indústria 4.0 programme (2017–2019) delivered tangible results across its strategic axes, mobilising hundreds of companies, institutions, and experts. From organisation of large-scale events to address the impact of digitalisation on the labour market and future skills needs to Open Shop Floor sessions, national innovation summits, and international partnerships, fostering knowledge exchange and practical demonstrations of Industry 4.0 adoption. Other events included the national exercise on cybersecurity and participation of innovative industries in the Hannover Messe. In the field of regulations, the programme developed online tools for standardisation maturity assessment and advanced cybersecurity awareness. While on the financial side, in collaboration with the European Investment Bank, the first phase proposed models for supporting and co-financing the digitalisation of SMEs.

The objective of **Phase II (2020-2021)**¹⁰ of the programme was to boost and generalise economic growth through digitalisation. Achieving this goal means that Portugal should modernise, reinforce and increase its businesses, workforce and related ecosystem’s competitiveness, by reaching and involving over 20.000 businesses operating in Portugal, re-skill and up-skill over 200.000 workers, addressing a challenge of a workforce that is still lagging behind as far as digital skills are concerned, and finance up to 350 transformative projects.

Phase II of the *Indústria 4.0* programme was structured around three guiding lines. The first, **Generalising I4.0**, looked to boost the sharing of knowledge, experiences, and benefits to stimulate a widespread transition to Industry 4.0. The second, **Capacity Building I4.0**, aimed to adapt workers’ knowledge and skills to ensure a smooth and inclusive transition. The third, **Assimilating I4.0**, focused on promoting, facilitating, and funding business access to Industry 4.0 methods and technologies, leveraging experimentation, scaling, and transformation.

Under this phase, eleven acceleration initiatives were launched to boost and generalise digital transformation across the economy¹¹. These included promoting self-diagnosis of digital maturity and supporting roadmaps for transformation (Digital Maturity Appraisals), providing

SME-focused training schemes (Digital and Sectorial Training), encouraging technology-driven entrepreneurship among university students (Innovation Stimulus), fostering digitisation and value chain integration between large companies, SMEs, and start-ups (Digital Linkages), and sharing knowledge from the application of Industry 4.0 technologies (Experience I4.0). The programme also aimed to create a collaborative national network of Digital Innovation Hubs as one-stop-shops for SMEs (Experimentation and Learning), deliver tailored training to managers and technicians (I4.0 Coaching), guide technological investment and organisational transformation (Funding and Transformation), improve access to investment and funding mechanisms (Access to Funding), develop cybersecurity support for SMEs (Risk and Innovation Management), and adapt funding and support lines to diverse project types to encourage scaling up and transformation (Funding and Transformation).

A core initiative was **Coaching 4.0**, a measure looking to support companies in adopting business models for the Digital Transition. The initiative promoted the integration of technology in companies, supporting the development of processes and organisational skills that foster the digital transformation of the organisations' business model. Its implementation consists of incentives for companies to support training and consultancy expenses to support digital transformation. With a total budget of 40 million euros, it is associated with an incentive system underpinning the policy aimed to **foster the digital maturity of companies**.

BOX 1 Digital Innovation Hubs

Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs)¹² are collaborative networks that include specific digital skills centres, with the aim of disseminating and adopting advanced digital technologies by companies, especially SMEs, through the development, testing and experimentation of these same technologies, aiming to increase competitiveness.

DIHs act as a gateway to the innovation ecosystem and a way to strengthen the ecosystem. DIHs result from cooperation between several partners with complementary skills and activities, including research centres, universities, incubators, competitiveness clusters, collaborative laboratories (Colabs), business associations, development agencies, among other actors in the national and regional innovation ecosystem.

To date, 17 DIHs operate in Portugal, with 3 of them officially designated European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) and thus receiving funding under the Digital Europe Programme (DIH PRODUTECH focusing on manufacturing digitalisation, PTCentroDIH focusing on digital and green transition for SMEs and public sector and AI4PA Portugal with focus on AI and data science for public sector).

For instance, the DIH PRODUTECH in Portugal focuses on the manufacturing sector, bringing together universities, research labs, startups and corporates to provide testing

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facilities, maturity diagnostics and matchmaking services for SMEs. Its mission is to drive innovation and competitiveness in the Portuguese manufacturing ecosystem through technology development and collaboration. It offers digital services tailored to manufacturing needs and fosters an ecosystem of equipment makers, software providers and reference manufacturing companies (metalworking, automotive, textiles, etc.).

2.1.2 Stakeholder mapping

The following table presents an **overview of main stakeholders** around the InCoDe.2030 programme and Industry 4.0 initiative in Portugal (intertwined for policy implementation), differentiating between public (national and EU level), private, educational and civil society sectors. The stakeholders mapping could go into further level of details, including a wider selection of regional and local stakeholders (see, for instance, Industry 4.0 initiative [strategic committee for phase I](#)).

Table 1 Indústria 4.0 & InCoDe.2030 Stakeholders and roles

Sector	Stakeholders	Role
Public Sector	Ministry of Science, Technology, and Higher Education [<i>including, Agência Nacional para a Qualificação e o Ensino Profissional (ANQEP), da Direção-Geral da Educação (DGE)</i>]	Oversees the implementation of the INCoDe.2030 Programme, focusing on enhancing digital skills across the population.
	Agência para o Desenvolvimento e Coesão (ADC)	Oversees EU fund usage for education and skill-building programs tied to digital transition.
	Observatório INCoDe.2030	Monitors and evaluates the INCoDe.2030 Program.
	Agência Nacional de Inovação (ANI)	Supports innovation and R&D activities related to digital transformation in both InCoDe-2030 and Industry 4.0 initiatives.
	Agência para a Competitividade e Inovação (IAPMEI)	Coordinates the Industry 4.0 Initiative, promoting the digital transformation of Portuguese industries.
	Institute for Employment and Vocational Training (IEFP)	Provides training and upskilling programMESs in digital skills for the unemployed and professionals (Upskill initiative)
	Agência para a Modernização Administrativa (AMA)	Focuses on digitalising public services and improving citizen interaction with government platforms (Ponto Digital)
	European Commission	Provides funding and policy guidance to align InCoDe-2030 and Industry 4.0 initiatives with broader European digital strategies.

Sector	Stakeholders	Role
Private Sector	Technology Companies (e.g., Altice, NOS, Vodafone Portugal)	Develop digital infrastructure and offer technological solutions supporting both initiatives. They also provide training programmes.
	Startup Ecosystem (e.g., Startup Portugal)	Supports tech startups in contributing to digital transformation.
	Digital Training Providers (e.g., Upskill, Code Academy Portugal)	Offer reskilling and upskilling programmes for tech careers.
	Industry Associations (e.g., COTEC Portugal)	Advocate for industry needs and facilitate collaboration between public and private sectors in both initiatives.
	Digital Innovation Hubs (e.g. Produtech, DIH4GlobalAutomotive, ATTRACT, etc.)	Provides support services and promotes digitalisation of key industries requiring specific I4.0 skills.
Educational Sector	Universities (e.g. Universidade de Lisboa, Universidade do Porto, Universidade do Aveiro)	Lead research and development in AI, cybersecurity, and big data.
	Polytechnic Institutes (e.g. Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa)	Provide applied digital skills training, especially in less urban areas.
Civil Society	Associação Portuguesa para o Desenvolvimento das Competências Digitais	Advocates for increased digital inclusion, particularly for vulnerable groups.
	Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT)	Funds and supports R&D in AI, big data, and digital literacy initiatives.

2.2 Policy implementation

The **implementation** of the various digital initiatives under Portugal Digital is coordinated among various stakeholders. The Portugal Digital Mission Structure – a coordinated body among diverse actors like ministries, national agencies, universities and business representatives – ensures overall coordination of the Action Plan and alignment with stakeholders. The structure was created in 2020, and in 2023 transferred its competencies to the Agency for Administrative Modernisation (AMA)¹³. This complements with other stakeholders that are responsible for implementing the different initiatives.

As umbrella initiative, **InCoDe.2030** is supported by three permanent bodies: the National Forum for Digital Competences, which unites public and private stakeholders and hosts an annual conference; the Coordination Structure, which manages and aligns all action lines and goals; and the Secretariat, which monitors activities, maintains platforms, and ensures communication between the Forum and Coordination Structure. Other institutions are supporting implementation from the technical side, including IEFP (Institute for Employment and Vocational Training), FCT (Foundation for Science and Technology), and APDC (Portuguese Association for the Development of Communications).

The **Indústria 4.0 initiative** has a governance model that aims to ensure the articulation and integration of efforts in the face of political cycles. The governance structures operate under

a pre-defined internal functioning model, supported by a clear set of responsibilities across various entities. The **Managing Entity** plays a central role in promoting and disseminating knowledge about the programme, mobilising and coordinating its operations, and developing critical tools for communication and collaboration among agents. It is also responsible for creating and managing the programme's digital platform, monitoring measures and their outcomes, and maintaining a repository of generated knowledge. The **Government Council** focuses on defining public policy guidelines, ensuring institutional sponsorship, coordinating with public bodies, and validating measures to be implemented at the public policy level. The **Steering Committee** provides strategic oversight through monitoring, orientation, and advice on diverse topics. The **Community of Experts** contributes by participating in working groups, discussing relevant subjects, offering technical assistance, and supporting the development and implementation of programme measures. Finally, **Working Groups and Different Entities** engage in debate and discussion on topics critical to the advancement of i4.0 and play a hands-on role in the development and execution of measures that drive the programme forward.

Figure 5 Indústria 4.0 Governance Model; Source: [COTEC](#)

2.2.1 Implementation gaps

The implementation of the digital transition strategy in Portugal, and in particular of the InCoDe.2030 programme and the Indústria 4.0 initiative, reveals a set of structural and operational gaps that have affected effectiveness, hindering progress towards a just transition.

First, **governance fragmentation and institutional instability** have limited strategic coherence. While a comprehensive architecture was formally established – with a Secretary of State for Digital Transition, a Mission Structure for Portugal Digital, the InCoDe.2030 Coordination Structure and Observatory, and, for Indústria 4.0, a Managing Entity supported by a Government Council, Steering Committee and Communities of Experts – in practice coordination has been weakened by frequent administrative reorganisations and shifting political priorities. Interviews evidence highlights that programmes were often assembled as **aggregations of pre-existing initiatives** rather than as parts of a coherent long-term implementation plan, with impact on limited continuity across political cycles and unclear hierarchical authority or coordination mechanisms between bodies responsible for skills, industrial policy, regional development and public administration.

Second, **limited implementation capacity at sub-national level** has generated uneven uptake. While metropolitan regions benefit from dense ecosystems of universities, polytechnics, clusters and business associations – mostly associated with the distribution of the industrial matrix – peripheral and ageing regions rely on thinner institutional infrastructures and face difficulties in mobilising companies and workers for digital transformation¹⁴¹⁵. Intermediary organisations such as local chambers of commerce and associations have played an important bridging role, but their resources and technical expertise vary widely. As a result, access to programmes such as Coaching 4.0, Digital Maturity Appraisals or specialised reskilling courses has been easier for companies already embedded in innovation networks, reinforcing pre-existing territorial and sectoral disparities.

Third, **financial and administrative requirements have created barriers for small and micro-enterprises in accessing actions promoted by the initiatives**. Although Indústria 4.0 and related Recovery and Resilience Plan instruments provide incentives for digital investment and training, co-financing rules, complex application procedures and the need for upfront resources availability favour larger companies and technologically advanced SMEs. Interviewees from industry clusters and DIHs stressed that many traditional manufacturing SMEs lack the managerial time, digital awareness and project-management capacity to engage with these schemes, even when funding is formally available. This has led to a concentration of participation among companies with higher absorptive capacity, in line with European Semester findings on the structural digital gap between large companies and SMEs¹⁶.

Fourth, **coordination between digital, education and industrial policies remains partial**. Universities and polytechnics are central providers of advanced digital skills, yet alignment between curricula, firm needs and regional development strategies is uneven. While flagship institutions in Lisbon, Porto and Coimbra are closely connected to Industry 4.0 initiatives and clusters, smaller regional institutions face difficulties in attracting resources and specialised

staff. At the same time, the out-migration of highly skilled graduates to metropolitan areas or abroad reduces the local impact of training investments, particularly in interior regions¹⁷.

Finally, **monitoring and feedback mechanisms have had limited influence on policy adjustment**. Although observatories, forums and expert groups exist, interview evidence points to weak systematic use of evaluation results to recalibrate targets, funding criteria or territorial focus. This issue is further developed in the next section on monitoring.

2.3 Policy monitoring and evaluation

Portugal's digital transition has been monitored mainly through EU-level datasets such as the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) and Eurostat, with complementary data available through the Portugal Digital Indicators portal. The INCoDe.2030 Observatory is the body formally responsible for monitoring the programme, carrying out continuous data collection and analysis using the Dynamic Reference Framework for Digital Competence (QDRCD) to assess progress in digital skills.

The main KPIs for InCoDe.2030 include:

- increasing digital literacy to 80% of the population by 2030;
- reducing the proportion of citizens without internet access to 5%;
- upskilling and reskilling over 200,000 workers for digital economy roles;
- supporting the digital transformation of 20,000 businesses;
- reaching 40% digital intensity among SMEs.

For Indústria 4.0, monitoring remains more limited and fragmented. The main indicators systematically tracked concern the proportion of enterprises providing ICT-related training and the number of employed ICT specialists, with no comprehensive set of outcome indicators capturing productivity effects, quality of employment, organisational change, or territorial distribution of impacts (See Figure below). Early initiatives such as UPskill and Coaching 4.0 have demonstrated positive results in terms of training participation and employability, but their long-term structural effects on firm performance, job quality and regional convergence are not yet systematically assessed.

Figure 6 Employed ICT specialists; Source: Observatorio InCoDe 2030

Evaluations are formally discussed within the National Forum for Digital Competences and through periodic reporting linked to the APDT and the Recovery and Resilience Plan. However, **monitoring frameworks remain largely input- and activity-oriented**, focusing on numbers of trainees, participating companies and funded projects, rather than on distributive outcomes. There is **limited systematic disaggregation of data**, which constrains the ability to assess whether the digital transition is reducing or reinforcing existing inequalities. At the strategic level, with the approval of the APDT, the Portuguese government defined a monitoring model based on a catalogue of 97 indicators, aligned with DESI and other EU benchmarks. This is a planned monitoring task, with no results published until now.

From the perspective of the European Semester¹⁸, Portugal continues to face challenges in translating digital and skills indicators into policy steering instruments that can guide targeted interventions for lagging SMEs, vulnerable workers and less-developed regions. The European Skills Index developed by CEDEFOP provides an overview of country skills landscape measuring “distance to ideal” performance^e. In 2024 evaluation, Portugal ranked 24th of 31 countries in the European Skills Index, with a total score of 45.3. At the pillar level, it ranked 27th in Skills Development (score: 36.9), 17th in Skills Activation (score: 61.9) and 25th in Skills Matching (score: 43.1). Figure 7 below shows a high number of skills utilisation and transition to work, evidencing a growing pattern of effectiveness of the national transition initiatives aimed at building skills (although not possible to disaggregate digital ones).

^e This ideal performance is chosen as the highest achieved by any country over a period of 7 years.

Figure 7 Overview of ESI skills pillars in Portugal, 2024; Source: CEDEFOP

Overall, while Portugal has developed an extensive statistical and institutional apparatus for monitoring digitalisation and skills, the current system remains fragmented across programmes and levels of governance and insufficiently focused on distributional impacts. This limits its capacity to support adaptive, equity-oriented policy learning in the context of Industry 4.0.

2.4 Synergies with other EU initiatives

The digitalisation initiatives in Portugal creates concrete synergies with different broader and cross-cutting EU domains. The following table summarises the main links between them.

Table 2 Synergies of Indústria 4.0 with other EU initiatives, per policy domain

Policy domain	Links	Examples
Regional domain	Digital inclusion and capacity-building efforts, particularly targeting rural areas and underserved populations, directly support the EU's Cohesion Policy objectives for balanced regional development.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resilience and Recovery Funds: Investments in digital infrastructure and skills in Portugal align with EU cohesion goals, particularly the EU's "Digital Compass" targets for 2030. - Regional Focus: Initiatives like Norte Digital contribute to regional competitiveness by enabling SMEs in less-developed regions to adopt digital technologies.
Social domain	Portugal's efforts to reskill and upskill its workforce align with the EU's European Skills Agenda and Pillar of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Upskill Programme: Reskilling unemployed and underemployed workers in ICT supports EU employment goals.

Policy domain	Links	Examples
	<p>Social Rights, which aim to prepare citizens for a green and digital economy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lifelong Learning Initiatives: Portugal’s focus on lifelong learning aligns with the EU’s target of 60% of adults participating in training by 2030. - Reducing Digital Exclusion: The focus on digital inclusion and literacy reduces social inequalities, in line with EU social cohesion policies.
<p>Economic domain</p>	<p>Digital transformation facilitates Portugal’s integration into global markets, aligning with EU trade and competition policies.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digitalisation of SMEs: Enhances Portugal’s export potential, particularly in high-tech sectors, supporting EU trade goals. - AI in Industry: Supports competitive EU industries by fostering innovation and digital competitiveness.
<p>Environmental domain</p>	<p>Digital technologies are key enablers of sustainability and energy transition, linking Portugal’s digital policies with EU environmental and energy goals, such as the European Green Deal.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industry 4.0 Initiatives: Digital transformation in industries improves energy efficiency and reduces waste. - AI and Big Data Applications: Encourage sustainable practices, such as smart grid optimization and precision agriculture, which support the EU’s climate neutrality targets.

3 Policy analysis

The digital transition in Portugal, and in particular the combination of InCoDe.2030 and the Indústria 4.0 initiative, is grounded in a **set of assumptions** that shape both its design and its distributive effects.

A first core assumption is that skills upgrading is inherently inclusive if access to training and digital technology is formally open. Usually, policy instruments are largely horizontal, relying on competitive calls, co-financing schemes and voluntary participation, with limited differentiation according to starting conditions¹⁹. In a context such as Portugal's, characterised by pronounced disparities in educational attainment, business size, innovation capacity and regional development, this design choice systematically advantages actors already close to the technological frontier and disadvantages those with lower institutional, financial and human capital endowments.

A second key assumption concerns the relationship between skills and labour-market. Policies are built on the expectation that expanding digital training will automatically translate into improved employability and productivity. In manufacturing, highly digitalised companies integrated into global production networks are better able to valorise advanced skills, offering career progression and wage premiums, while traditional SMEs often lack the organisational capacity to redesign jobs or upgrade work organisation²⁰. As a result, even when workers acquire digital skills, this may not translate into improvements in job quality for large segments of the workforce.

Interviews confirmed that upskilling programmes include trainings that are offered where corporate demand is highest (notably, metropolitan areas). While rural candidates could apply, *“course availability is concentrated in regions where companies request talent (e.g., Lisbon or Porto).”* This creates a territorial digital divide: metropolitan economies keep modernising, while remote areas see little infusion of digital capital.

While looking at the Portuguese skills landscape, we can observe an increase in the training of personnel to develop ICT skills, particularly among enterprises with 250 or more employees, which recorded a 16% rise between 2016 and 2024 (Figure 8 below). Since 2019, there has also been a slight increase in the proportion of enterprises choosing to train their staff rather than hire ICT specialists (Figure 9). This trend is especially clear among SMEs, that may have less capacity to undergo trainings at home or absorptive capacity to send an employee for a training period, tightening the internal workload. An interviewee described: *“SMEs don't have enough time, money and skills to follow a digitalisation process... even if they received money and incentives, it is always the big companies that benefit most because they have the necessary resources.”* Even where courses were free, they often conflicted with SMEs day-to-day needs: *“managers underestimate the importance of reskilling; if courses mean taking time off work, participation drops.”*

From a labour-market perspective, these dynamics reflect a broader tension between skill formation and adjustment mechanisms, as existing policy frameworks tend to emphasise reskilling rather than the development of structured career transition pathways necessary to manage technological displacement effectively (Frey, 2019; Calvino et.al., 2018).

Figure 8 Enterprises providing training to their personnel to develop their ICT skills; Source: authors, based on Observatorio InCoDe 2030

Figure 9 Enterprises that didn't employ ICT specialists but provided training to their personnel to develop their ICT skills; Source: authors, based on Portugal National Institute for Statistics

The post-2020 period (following the first phase of the Indústria 4.0 programme) shows a clear increase in the share of companies investing in digital training. High-technology industries (such as chemicals, electronics, and mechanical engineering) invest more heavily in training due to their higher absorptive capacity, stronger integration in global value chains, and greater reliance on advanced digital technologies. In contrast, traditional sectors — including food, beverages, textiles, and wood-based industries — exhibit lower levels of investment. This can be explained by structural constraints such as lower profit margins, higher relative training costs, less skilled workforces, and weaker incentives to adopt advanced digital solutions (OECD, 2021; Eiffe and Riso, 2025).

However, one barrier is the afterwards of the training processes: *“no one [in the company] knew what to do with those competences afterwards.”* Interviewees explained that often managers had difficulties with re-organising workflows. The oversight and evaluation phases of programmes often fail to capture this: surveys report high satisfaction with courses, but informal follow-up reveals many companies reverted to “business-as-usual” after the training process ended.

Figure 10 Enterprises providing training to their personnel to develop ICT skills by manufacturing sector; Source: authors, based on Portugal National Institute for Statistics)

3.1 Drivers of inequalities in digital transition policies

Building up on the previous sections, there are **five primary drivers** of inequalities embedded in Portugal’s digitalisation policies. The table below summarises the drivers with a brief description.

Table 3 Drivers

Drivers	Subcategory	Definition
Economic dynamics	Governance arrangements	Fragmented multi-level governance and complex implementation structures that advantage actors with stronger administrative resources and network embeddedness.
	Labour-market segmentation	Dual employment structures and selective access to training lead to unequal translation of digital skillsets in working environment
Institutional capacities	Financial and investment structures	Co-financing requirements and credit constraints and administrative complexity favouring large and technologically advanced companies over SMEs.
	Demographic distribution and economic matrix	Concentration of universities and business clusters in metropolitan regions creates cumulative advantages and reinforces regional disparities.

Drivers	Subcategory	Definition
Technology developments	Automation & AI raise	Automation and AI generate labour polarisation, highlighting a timing gap between technology change and re/up-skilling processes.
Regulatory framework	Access to (EU) funding mechanisms	Usually, funding frameworks favour “ready” companies and can unintentionally widen gaps between actors in terms of their absorptive capacity.

Governance arrangements constitute a primary driver of inequality, particularly at the policy design phase. The digital transition is implemented through a complex constellation of ministries, agencies, observatories, clusters and intermediary actors. While this multi-actor configuration reflects the cross-cutting nature of digitalisation, it also generates fragmentation and uneven steering capacity. Actors with strong administrative resources, project-management expertise and stable institutional positioning are usually better equipped to navigate this system, participate in consultations, influence priorities and secure funding. Peripheral regions, small local authorities and micro-enterprises, by contrast, face difficulties in accessing information, preparing applications and sustaining participation in networks. The multilevel coordination is, however, a limitation that exceeds digital transition policies in Portugal.

Interviews suggested that InCoDe.2030 and Indústria 4.0 have largely focused on the supply side (training workers) rather than the demand side (preparing companies). In this direction, policy discussions rarely included how to change training processes, business ownership or work cultures to absorb digital talent. The lack of organisational readiness was attributed to the cross-ministerial divide: educational agencies design curricula, while economic agencies leave companies management to private sector.

Financial instruments also play a central role in creating unequal outcomes especially at the policy implementation level. Digital transformation in manufacturing entails high upfront investment, much of it in intangible assets such as software, data infrastructure, cybersecurity and organisational change. Public support schemes typically require co-financing and complex reporting. This creates a structural advantage for large companies and technologically mature SMEs, which can mobilise internal resources and pre-finance projects. Smaller businesses in traditional sectors, often located in less-developed regions and operating with low margins, face financial and administrative constraints that limit their ability to participate. As an interviewee explained *“big companies benefit from access to European incentives because they have the resources to match funding, but also because some funding is directed to specific sectors.”*

Labour-market dynamics constitute another relevant driver in transition policies affecting both policy design and implementation stages. Portugal’s high incidence of temporary employment and the strong segmentation between core and peripheral workers shape access to training and exposure to technological change. Interviews affirmed that companies tend to invest in upskilling permanent employees, while workers in temporary, subcontracted or low-qualified positions receive less support. Interviews confirmed that sometimes manager faced difficulties in understanding the importance of reskilling processes.

Territorial factors further interact with these market dynamics. Although broadband coverage has expanded significantly, the effective capacity to engage in Industry 4.0 is strongly concentrated in metropolitan and coastal regions, where universities, research centres, key business clusters and specialised service providers are located. Big agglomerations attract talent, investment and projects, creating further territorial socio-economic benefits. Interior and rural regions, affected by demographic ageing and out-migration of skilled workers, encounter greater difficulties in mobilising businesses and workers for digital transformation.

Technological developments themselves act as indirect drivers of inequality affecting the whole policy cycle. Industry 4.0 and the diffusion of AI and advanced automation are associated with job polarisation, increasing demand for high-level technical, analytical and managerial skills. In the absence of strong organisational innovation and social dialogue, this can lead to work intensification and employment insecurity. Policies that focus primarily on technological adoption and skills supply, without equally addressing work organisation and career pathways could re-create new forms of inequality emerging alongside traditional ones. An interviewee explained: *“A lot of people do not understand the relevance of digital sources and what is behind technological features. The digital era – everyone speaks of that – but no one could say all the things it could imply.”*

An associated issue with the development of technology is the timing gap. Interviewees working with reskilling or upskilling processes with companies experienced difficulties in making companies forecast skill needs in certain period ahead, instead of focusing on current gaps. This makes trainings outdated compared to rhythm of technological developments: by the time re-skilling is achieved, the skill target may have moved: *“people are wondering if these courses still make sense when every few months a new technology emerges”*, as one interviewee notes.

At a broader level, the **regulatory framework** also shapes inequality outcomes. Different funding mechanisms impact diversely in the way actors were able to access EU level funding and deepen digital transition. In similar way as seen with national financial instruments, this can favour actors with higher readiness level and implementation capacity.

3.2 From policy assumptions to distributed outcomes

This section presents the overview of inequalities underpinning Portugal’s digital transition policies in the manufacturing sector. The summary below presents an overview of factors linking policy assumptions, resources and governance arrangements as well as intended outcomes. Particularly, it highlights where inequalities emerge along the policy cycle, from policy design, through implementation to monitoring and evaluation.

The illustration provides a structured basis for identifying critical leverage points for policy adjustment. It helps to clarify how horizontal and technically ‘inclusive’ policy instruments can nevertheless generate differentiated effects across companies, workers and territories. Moreover, it allows for the detection of bottlenecks, coordination failures and unintended distributive effects of the digital policy in Portugal.

Figure 11 Summary table on Portugal's digital transition

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4 Conclusions

Portugal has made significant progress in building a comprehensive cluster of initiatives for digital transition, combining digital skills development, business digitalisation and public administration modernisation in line with the EU Digital Decade. The InCoDe.2030 programme and the Indústria 4.0 initiative illustrate a strong commitment to fostering technological adoption and reskilling in the manufacturing sector.

These initiatives have evidenced success in terms of achieving their core aim of upskilling participants. For the labour market, these pathways – from unemployed to tech worker – represent significant social mobility steps for individuals who might otherwise have remained on welfare. Moreover, the initiatives have raised awareness and interest in digitalisation and Industry 4.0 concept, contributing to keep widen competitiveness of manufacturing sector in the international market. However, this case study reveals **inequalities emerging across diverse phases of the policy cycle**, from design to implementation and monitoring, creating an uneven landscape of transition.

Inequalities are not merely residual effects but are rooted in the interaction between pre-existing practices of policy designs and asymmetries in institutional capacity, labour-market segmentation and territorial development. Governance fragmentation, selective access to finance and training and the concentration of innovation ecosystems in metropolitan regions contribute to differentiated abilities to access to or benefit from digitalisation. As a result, large companies, highly skilled workers and core regions are better positioned to capture the gains of Industry 4.0, while SMEs in traditional sectors, vulnerable workers and peripheral territories face higher adjustment costs and greater risks of exclusion.

These findings illustrate a policy challenge: Portugal has built well-considered programmes to bridge its digital divide, but the structural features of its economy and governance are limiting the outcomes in unintended and diverse directions. The result is not a uniform digitalisation process in manufacturing sector but rather a *distributed transition*. This is not due to lack of awareness among policymakers, but it rather reflects the complexity of addressing cross-cutting challenges in a fragmented institutional landscape.

From a just transition perspective, this case highlights the need to complement technological and skills policies with **stronger distributive and place-based instruments**. This includes, for instance: strengthening coordination across policy domains and levels of governance; tailoring financial and advisory support to the needs of small companies and less-developed regions; make available funding resources at national and regional level with simplified administrative mechanisms that favour cohesive distribution of opportunities; ensuring that reskilling strategies explicitly target workers most exposed to automation and job transformation, while keeping the door open for new-workers to market; and developing transparent and continuously updated monitoring systems.

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